

IMPLEMENTATION OF CHARACTER EDUCATION IN REALIZING THE DISCIPLINE OF VOCATIONAL MIDDLE SCHOOL STUDENTS

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Abstract

This research occurs because of the phenomenon of students who deviate from human character through a descriptive qualitative approach and to find out and analyze the planning, implementation, and follow-up of character education to improve student discipline. The research data was obtained through interviews, documentation studies and observations of students and all stakeholders in the school. The results showed that the character education process carried out in vocational schools integrated character values in all school activities, both curricular and extracurricular activities and the implementation in this study showed that character education management to improve student discipline can be carried out properly so that vocational students can find an identity that has character and can be applied in the World of Work and the Industrial World as well as in everyday life.

Keywords : Implementation , Character Education and Discipline

A. PRELIMINARY

The development of the nation's character also depends on the educational process, which must be based on the concepts of humanist educational psychology. However, the negative phenomenon that is currently happening is that attitudes, thoughts, and behaviours of free citizens emerge. Wild and out of control. The complexity of change causes conflicts of interest, disorientation in values and functions, and conflicts. Complexity appears along with changes that give birth to wild and uncontrollable behaviour causing the weakening and loss of the values of truth, honesty, sense of justice, humanity, and civility.

This study aims to obtain an overview of the implementation of character education in order to improve the discipline of Vocational High School students. This is very necessary for the proper management of character education in order to realize the ideal national character. Terry (1986) as quoted by Hasibuan Malayu SP (1996:74) views management as a process, as follows: “ *Management is a distinct process consisting of planning, organizing, actuating, and controlling performed to determine and accomplish stated objectives by the use of human being and other resources* ”. Therefore, the implementation of character education includes: 1) planning 2) implementation 3) follow-up which of course must receive important attention for all parties involved in the world of education. This research can be formulated as follows: The raw input empowerment is not optimal yet learners. The use of instrumental input includes the curriculum, resources for educators and education personnel, infrastructure, and costs. The environmental input, which consists of families, communities and stakeholders, is not optimally involved in the character education management process which is based on the principles of humanist education.

In line with. The management functions referred to by Morris (Sudjana, 2000:34) are:

A series of various reasonable activities have been determined and have a relationship and interdependence between one another and are carried out by people, organizations or parts thereof, who are assigned the task of carrying out these activities.

This is in line with the opinion of Elkind and Sweet (in the Ministry of National Education, 2010:13), which states that character education is defined as follows: "Character education is the deliberate effort to help people understand, care about, and act upon core ethical values." Character education is a deliberate effort to help people understand, care and act according to ethical values.

Substantive character in the concept of good character proposed by Aristotle is "*...the life of right conduct-right conduct in relations to other persons and in relation to oneself*" (Lickona, 199).

Based on the formulation of the problem above, the research is limited to:

1. What activities are carried out in planning character education in realizing student discipline in Vocational High Schools?
2. What activities are carried out in the implementing of character education programs in realizing student discipline in Vocational High Schools?
3. What activities are carried out in the follow-up of character education in realizing student discipline in Vocational High Schools?

B. RESEARCH METHODS

According to Arikunto (2006), the descriptive qualitative approach is generally non-hypothetical research, so the research step does not need a hypothesis. Instead, the descriptive qualitative used is exploratory, which aims to describe certain circumstances or phenomena. This research is based on a "phenomenological" approach to rediscovering basic experiences in the form of norms adopted in a community concerning aspects of education and other education-related problems.

As stated by Suyatna Basar Atmadjan in Laksmi (2001: 33), the descriptive method states: "Descriptive research aims to describe or describe the current state of a person, institution or society based on the facts that appear only in the situation being investigated.

C. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Student Character Education Planning Activities

Activities to set goals to be achieved must be planned, how to achieve these goals, and how to evaluate the achievement of the goals. Character education is very important because character education, as expressed by Mulyasa (2011:7)

A system of inculcating character values in students includes components of awareness, understanding, concern, and a high commitment to implementing these values, both towards

Allah SWT, others, the environment, society, and the nation so that they become human perfectly by its nature.

Therefore, careful planning is needed, neatly arranged so that the objectives of this program can be achieved properly..

The results of research in Vocational High Schools, The role of the principal in planning the implementation of character education with other stakeholders has outlined the school's vision, mission and goals. In addition, the school's vision has described the character values students must achieve during their education at the vocational high school.

Vision in a school is a moral expectation that describes the desired school profile in the future. However, such hope for the future will always be coloured by opportunities and challenges that are believed to occur in the future. Therefore, schools must pay attention to future developments and challenges in determining their Vision. In Vocational High School, this has been stated in the school's Vision, namely by including the relevance of education to face the era of globalization.

Mission statement regarding the things that the organization must achieve for interested parties in the future (Akdon, 2001 9: 97). The mission statement reflects the description of the product or service offered.

A mission is an action or effort to realize the vision. So the mission is the elaboration of the vision in the form of the formulation of tasks, obligations, and action plans used as directions to realize the vision. In other words, the mission is a form of service to meet the demands outlined in the vision.

Planning is very important in implementing character education because it can affect all stakeholders in the school. There are several forms of implementation planning in schools that Vocational High Schools, namely have carried out:

- a) Create a vision and mission;
- b) Making RKS and RKAS;
- c) Making policies and setting goals and indicators for their achievement;
- d) Designing programs;
- e) Define and allocate resources;
- f) Modify the work plan.

2. Activities in the Implementation of Character Education for Students

The implementation of character education in learning in Vocational High Schools is applied in everyday life. Thus this refers to the government's expectations as outlined in the Grand Design character education manual, which states that character education must be integrated into learning in every subject related to norms and values. Each subject must be developed, made explicit, and linked to the context of everyday life. The learning of character values does not stop at the cognitive level but touches on the level of internalization and real practice in the daily lives of students in society.

The implementation of character education requires commitment from all school members. Educators, education personnel, school staff and others are expected to be good role models in developing the character that has been declared. Therefore, Vocational High Schools always carry out regular coaching, which is not only coaching for students but also important. guidance for all educators and education staff, either by the principal directly or by other parties who are considered competent.

The main activities carried out in the implementation of character education in Vocational High Schools are through:

- a) spiritual habituation activities,
- b) In KBM,
- c) inculcating the value of discipline,
- d) exemplary,
- e) Co-curricular and extra-curricular activities,
- f) Instilling the value of responsibility

The guideline for developing character education states that: The values developed in cultural and national character education are identified from the following sources: Religion, culture, Pancasila, and National education goals where these values are developed in schools through integration in learning, habituation activities and student activities.

Character education activities are carried out through habituation activities. This activity is carried out by all school residents and is carried out continuously. As stated by Ratna Megawangi (2004), namely that:

Character education educates a person to become accustomed to good behaviour so that he becomes accustomed and will feel guilty if he does not.

3. Follow-up Activities for the Implementation of Character Education for Students

The results of the assessment carried out by the teacher can be correct and objective. The school carries out its assessments based on correct assessment principles by the assessment standards set by the assessment experts. The assessment is carried out as expected by the Government (Kemdiknas / Kemdikbud), namely, by Government Regulation of the Republic of Indonesia, Number 57 of 2021 concerning National Education Standards Article 16. In this standard, many techniques and forms of assessment are offered to conduct an assessment, including character assessment. In character assessment, teachers should make an assessment instrument equipped with an assessment rubric to avoid subjective assessments, both in observational assessment instruments (observation sheets) and attitude scale assessment instruments (e.g. Likert scale).

The activities carried out in the assessment of character education go through the following stages:

- a) **Assessment criteria:** The assessment is carried out qualitatively, and its success is more determined by the process and participation of students,

- b) **Assessment Techniques:** Attitude assessment is done through observation, self-assessment, and assessment between students. Skills assessment is carried out through demonstration of skills,
- c) **Assessment Media:** Can be in the form of journals and portfolios,
- d) **Assessment Process:** The assessment process is carried out every time you practice and every day in the learning process. Moreover, the process of assessing scouting education as an extracurricular must focus on the domain of attitude values; scouting skills are supporters of the assessment of scouting education itself. The attitude assessment process is carried out using the observation method and can be carried out by friends, subject teachers, stakeholders or scouting coaches.
- e) **Assessment mechanism:** The pattern of implementation of the assessment in the education unit includes work program planning, training programs, and implementation.

Given that the nature of vocational education is that graduates are ready to work, the character education developed is character education that is relevant to work needs. According to Slamet PH (2011), the character of work for vocational education is divided into two dimensions: intrapersonal and interpersonal. The intrapersonal dimension of work is an inner or spiritual quality, including work ethic, curiosity, self-discipline, honesty, responsibility, self-respect, hard work, integrity, perseverance, work motivation, flexibility, humility, like the unknown, Etc. On the other hand, interpersonal dimensions are skills related to human relations, including being responsible for all their actions, being able to work together, respecting others, adapting, liking peace, always solidarity, leadership, commitment, fairness and so on.

In implementing this character education, there are values to create a cultured nation through strengthening religious values, honesty, tolerance, discipline, hard work, creativity, independence, democracy, curiosity, national spirit, love for the homeland and responsibility. All of which must be provided in the implementation of the educational process in school education units integrated into intra-curricular, co-curricular and extracurricular activities. In the implementation in schools, the values of Character Education in extracurricular activities are to strengthen character values through strengthening learning materials and learning methods that are by curriculum content based on laws and regulations. Extracurricular activities strengthen character values to expand students' potential, talents, interests, abilities, personalities, cooperation and independence. Meanwhile, in co-curricular activities, it is a strengthening of character values which is carried out for deepening and enriching intra-curricular activities of curriculum content.

D. CONCLUSION

Based on the results of research in Vocational High Schools in general, it can be concluded that character education management to improve student discipline has been carried out with the planning, implementation and follow-up functions. Effective and efficient education management in Vocational High Schools has collaborated with school principals, teachers, and

committees. The obstacles that occur are overcome properly so they can be overcome and show progress. In particular, it can be concluded as follows:

Character education planning is outlined in the school's vision, mission and goals, which is then outlined in the preparation of learning, in which basically every subject contains materials related to character. Character education in Vocational High Schools leads to the formation of school culture from the values that underlie behaviour, traditions, daily habits and symbols practised by all school members and the community around the school. School culture is the character or character, the school's image and the school's characteristics in the wider community. There are several forms of planning in schools that Vocational High Schools, namely have implemented: making a vision and mission, formulating school goals, making policies and setting goals, planning programs, determining and allocating resources and modifying work plans.

The implementation of character education in Vocational High Schools, namely in developing the values that form the basis of character education, is carried out through all subjects in the curriculum. The implementation is in the form of developing the values that are internalized in learning planning, such as the learning syllabus and lesson plans that already include the values and character goals for each basic competency to be achieved by students, so that in the learning steps the character that the teacher will build is reflected in the learning process. Learning and evaluation plans consist of an observation format for the development of the character values of students. The steps of the learning process have reflected the instilling of character values into students. Vocational High Schools carry out character education through habituation, exemplary and extracurricular activities, and mandatory or extracurricular options. Habituation and exemplary activities are carried out by all school members, which are applied continuously and continuously.

Assessment and evaluation activities are carried out during the learning process and at the end of the lesson. The evaluation activities in the administration of the development of character values it has been well administered so that at the end of the assessment, there appears to be continuity. The results of the development of character values already have a special format to be reported periodically to parents; the column in the report card is only limited to the personality column.

The implementation of character education has to support and inhibit factors. Character education is expected at this Vocational High School to be carried out well thanks to the support of various parties such as all school components from the principal, teachers, staff and students. Where in planning, the principal commits with all school residents, then the implementation is carried out by all school residents in their respective capacities based on the agreed commitments. As a result, school programs have been well administered, and school activities in the form of reporting administration have been made well so that the development of character education can be monitored.

The follow-up of Character Education in Vocational High Schools is by integrating the form of extracurricular, co-curricular and extracurricular activities so that they can be mixed and

matched according to the needs of the World of Work and the Industrial World by using Intrapersonal and Interpersonal Dimensions.

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